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Evaluation of Self Help Community Development Projects In Zungeru in Niger State, Nigeria

By

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Community infrastructural projects are basic requirements by any settlement for its effective and proper functioning and vital for the overall regional development of the area. The objectives of this study are to appraise the physical community projects by social groups/organization and government in Zungeru, examine the impact of self help community development efforts in the area, review problems associated with community development organizations and finally attempt physical planning measures to ensure effective CBOs development efforts in the study area. Data were procured through primary and secondary source and simple analytical statistical frequency methods were utilized. Various community based projects were found to have been executed by both the private organizations and the government but with little impact. To resolve the problems of effective community facility provision in the study area, it is recommended among other things that physical planning must be embraced since it involves the creation of functionally efficient and aesthetically friendly environment for living, working, circulation and recreation, the government should make available institutions that extend credit facilities at very low interest rate to CBOs for projects development and above all, the Federal government should encourage and assist the states, local government areas and communities in infrastructural development drives.

Keywords: Community development, Community self help projects, Community infrastructures.

INTRODUCTION

According to Ola (2004), infrastructure generally are community services such as communication, health, education and security that are fundamental to the society where they are provided as statutory right to everybody. Community infrastructural projects, therefore, are basic requirements by any settlement for its effective and proper functioning and vital for the overall regional development of the area. Frishchmann (2007) observed that no modern settlement can survive on its own without adequate provision of community infrastructural facilities such as modern markets, water facilities, adequate roads network system, health facilities, communication network facilities and many others to mention a few. The provision of adequate and functional community infrastructure has direct bearing on the economic and overall growth of any community. The poor state of infrastructural facilities in most communities has been a major factor responsible for the slow pace of industrialization of the country. The problems of low and epileptic electricity supply, inadequate and unreliable water supply, and poor telecommunication network have affected industrial activities and establishments and consequently results into high cost of production. The poor state of rural and urban road net work system have brought bottlenecks in the movement of goods and services in the country.

The provision of infrastructural facilities in any settlement directly or indirectly affects the standard of living of the individuals in that community. Mabogunje (1993) observed that infrastructural provision on an extensive, continuous and self sustaining basis is a sine- qua- non for the efficiency of operation and urban enterprises and the livability of cities; and that infrastructure is the crux of modern urban development.

Consequent upon the recognition of the relevance of infrastructure in the development of our communities, various efforts have been made available over the years by the government and private organizations to develop strategies and policies to spread these services to all segments of human settlements. As a result of the global economic recession which adversely affects the third world countries with low financial base to cope with unlimited financial responsibilities, the rural areas have been subjected to high level of deprivation and neglect.

The above situation has compelled the rural communities to adopt communal actions in addressing community facilities development following the adage that "he that is neglected does not neglect himself". This leads to the concept of self help projects. It is a process whereby the community itself is responsible for initiating, planning, organizing and directing its own efforts with little or no assistances from the government to achieve its desired goal of community development. Accordingly, Ogbonna, (1999) asserts that self help projects rely more on the local resources, community labour and managerial ability of the people concerned.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Zungeru is an old historical town in Wushishi L.G.A of Niger state with considerable potentials for undertaking and promoting participation in development activities but the potentials are subjected to both human and natural problems. The dearth of infrastructural facilities and services has been a major set back against the development of most communities in the local government area and other parts of the country, of which Zungeru is not an exception. The community has found it hard to meet up with the pace of modernization and as well contribute effectively to the overall national development.

The study area was once the administrative headquarters of the then northern Nigeria and it attracted therefore all forms of infrastructural and community facilities but when the capital was moved out to Kaduna, the town has suffered great deal of deprivation and neglect by the government in terms of facilities provision (Ibrahim, 2008).

Objectives:

The objectives of this study are to

- Examine the projects undertaken by the various social groups/organizations and governments in the area
- Examine the impact of self help community development efforts in the town
- Review the problems against the performance of community organization on self help projects in the area
- Attempt physical planning measures for ensuring the effective participation of CBOs in Community infrastructural projects development.

MATERIALS SOURCES AND METHODS

Sources of data collection:

The materials for this study were obtained through primary and secondary sources

i. Primary Sources

This involved direct field work, oral interviews, administration of questionnaires and the snapping of photographs. Data on socio-economic characteristics, housing and infrastructural facilities are handled here.

ii. Secondary Sources:

Various text books, journals, mimeographs and past students projects were utilized for the procurement of data for this study. The internet was also adequately explored.

The data were interpreted and analyzed by the use of Simple frequency tables and percentage frequencies. The use of descriptive statistic was also employed to describe the observed data from the field.

THE STUDY AREA

Location and Historical Evolution of Zungeru:

Zungeru is a traditional town in Wushishi L.G.A of Niger state (see fig.1). It is about 60 kilometers from the state capital of Minna and about 160 kilometers from Kontagora in Kontagora Local Government Area of Niger state.

Fig. 1: Zungeru in Wushishi Local Government Area of Niger State
Source: Department of Urban and Regional Planning, F.U.T, Minna

The population of the area was put at 8, 347 (1991) (National Population Commission) with an annual growth rate of 2.83%, and with an estimated population of 15, 423 in 2012.

According to Mohammed (1994) as cited by Sanusi (2005), the town is said to be a Gwari settlement, whose origin can be traced to one man Nda, who settled at the river Nanamaye in Zungeru for fishing and thereby entertained his customers with a native guitar, but this further led to an expanded settlement around him and named it Dunguru because of its musical instrument. This name became the town's traditional name until the arrival of the colonial masters who mis called the name as Zungeru because of their difficulties in its pronunciation.

Zungeru was part of the Sokoto caliphate during the reign of Usman Zaki as the first Emir (Sanusi, 2005). The traditional administration of the town continued until the advent of the colonial administrator in the country.

By the year 1916, with the movement of the seat of government from the town to Kaduna, the traditional system of governance was further up in places in the area, under the chief of Wushishi.

POTENTIALS FOR COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN ZUNGERU

Transportation Facilities:

All over the world, transportation facilities are important integral parts of the process of development of a community (Kunle, 2004, Robinson et al, 1978). As a traditional colonial settlement, Zungeru has opportunity to modern transportation network; it has road networks and rail ways that link the town up with other major settlements such as Kaduna, Kano, Katsina to the north and Lagos, Ibadan, Ilorin, Abeokuta, etc to the south. The study area has good and reliable road networks that link the town with the state capital of Minna and other towns in the state such as Wushishi, Bida and Mariga.

Educational Facilities:

The study area is also blessed with some grades of educational institutions, like nursery, primary secondary and post secondary schools.

Health Facilities:

There is one public and many private primary health centres in the community that cater for the health needs of the people in the area. It is generally noted that the health status of the Nigerian people is poor, with the nutritional status also poor (Ola, 2004). It has been estimated that only about 57 percent of the country's population has access to modern health care services, with urban centres having a better share than the rural area (Phillips, 1997).

Commercial Facilities:

There are two main markets in the area. They are the daily and weekly markets, which attract many traders from within and outside the state on every market day. The effect of these markets in terms of creation of credit for those who engage in trading in this community cannot be overemphasized. Zungeru and the settlements in its environs are noted for the cultivation of agricultural produce such as rice, beans, corn, sorghum and yam in large commercial quantity. There is also the presence of numerous locked up shops in all the nooks and crannies of the town especially along the major streets. These shops are involved in wholesale and retailing of goods to customers within the study area. There are many filling petrol stations that distribute fuel to private and commercial vehicle owners in the area.

Human Resources:

The rate of growth of population in the area affords it with an energetic human resource base for the promotion of community development efforts.

Apart from the above mentioned resources as potentials for accelerated community growth and development there are other resources such as the rivers Kaduna and Nanamaye. These two natural rivers can be harnessed for hydro electric power generation and for irrigation purpose. As a result of the presence of these rivers fishing flourishes in the area.

Moreover, the presence of the rivers affords the community ample opportunity for regular and constant water supply for domestic, commercial and industrial purposes. Water is a major problem to most Nigerian communities, especially in urban environments.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK:

Anuncha (1992) has identified community as a geographically determined area where educative, social, civil and political factors affect the membership and where a group of people reside and work together towards common goals. This situation implies that the people in the same community have a sense of belonging and have common values, norms and interest.

Development, on the other hand, has been operationalized by Oni (1985) as a continuous process of positive and progressive changes in the quality and span of life of the people. The concept of development can also be perceived in terms of improvement in the economic, polity, technology and culture of a people.

Therefore, community development is seen as a process of social action in which people of a particular community organize themselves for identification of their needs for planning and action to meet those with maximum reliance on their own initiative and resources, supplemented with assistance in any form, by government or non – governmental organization. In other words, community development is a process in which various communities identify their problems and initiate workable experiences to supply their own needs.

In the works of Author (1960), community development is seen as a method of helping local communities to become aware of the needs to assess their resources more realistically to organize themselves and resources in such a way as to satisfy some of their needs and by so doing accrue the attitude, experiences and co-operatives skill for reporting this process repeatedly on their own efforts. Community infrastructure according to Idachaba (2005) consists of physical, social and institutional forms of capital which aid community residents in the production, movement distribution and consumption activities, as well as enhances the quality of community life.

As asserted by the World Bank (1994), the provision of community infrastructure is essential to health, national prosperity and business. Accordingly, Isma (1993) has maintained that the existence of satisfactory

infrastructure is a pre-requisite of sustainable private sector investment in industry and commerce and without which any effort to realize the objective of economic development plans are futile and inevitably abortive.

Thus it was suggested by Sudhi and Yashi (1995) that investment in infrastructure and the associated provision of services are integral to the process of community development and infrastructural investment was identified as playing key role in agricultural production and as well facilitating the growth of the developing countries.

To further debunk the relevance of community infrastructural provision in community development, James (2003) has echoed the needs for developing countries governments to set the stage for better infrastructural provision by promoting good governance and making key regulatory reforms to improve the investment leverage of private sector investment. These needs, he suggested, are vast from the slum to the remote country side.

Planning for community infrastructural development should, therefore, take into account of diversities in economic, social and cultural set-up in such settlements. The hierarchy of settlements according to Egunjobi (1997), should therefore, determine the type, number and quality of services to be provided. Thus, the pattern of relationship existing among settlements and the population density should be used in delimiting the boundaries of services area of facility.

The non - governmental organizations (NGOs) according to Ogbnozobe (2000) have been responsible positively for various forms of physical community infrastructural development in Nigeria, through diverse developmental activities of community based organizations (CBOs) participation in infrastructural provision. It follows, therefore, that not only is it a means of increasing efficiency, but it also strengthens the sense of community ownership of projects and ensures transparency and accountability in project planning and implementation. In that regard, it must be noted that when CBOs and other stakeholders bear part of the cost of providing infrastructural services, their commitment to the success of the project is greater.

The self help infrastructure development programme as identified by Nwosu (1987) is a good strategy for community development with the realization and acceptance of the fact that people recognize that government resource are not unlimited and given the limited resources government can not provide all the needs of all the communities at the same time. In the process, communities which are relatively in a hurry have always taken recourse to "self-help" and "self-help" has appeared to be a development philosophy embraced more by the rural communities than the urban communities.

Community development through infrastructural tool can not be achieved without any proper administrative and institutional frame work in motion. The institutional frame work, according to Oduala, (1987) is essential not only for routine administrative work but for accelerated improvement in the living conditions of people in the undeveloped communities in Nigeria.

In the works of Koinyan (1993), it is important to go beyond the provision of infrastructure in community development because infrastructure where available facilitates the development process but it is the massive participation of the entire populace in the production activities on a self sustaining and self reliant basis that really constitute true development. He, therefore, suggested that the provision of infrastructures and production activities must go together and one without the other will constitute an extremely flawed development process.

CONCEPTS OF SELF HELP IN COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

Observation has been made that communities prefer the arrangement where they define their own development goals, formulate their needs and get government authorities to provide them with technical and financial assistances where necessary. However, self help project is a result of out growth of felt needs. This is the recognition of the important necessity or usefulness of a project which determines the decision to undertake such projects and to a large extent determines the successful completion.

According to Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary "self-help" is the act of relying on your own efforts and abilities in order to solve your problems, rather than depending on other people for help". Ekuma (1977) asserted that it is not for a leader to decide what the people want but to find those areas of priority such as electricity project, water schemes and health centres etc and carry his people along, with firm. This can be achieved through discussion in family meetings and public conferences. The fact in this statement is that there is no single person either by his position or influence in the society or community that can impose any decision or has the sole right to make decision for the community on what project to embark upon.

Another important element of a successful self-help community development project as noted by Olisa et al (1992) relies on government assistances. It has been noted from the work that communities tend to achieve greater success in implementing their chosen self help project if they receive assistances from the government in the form of money and other technical inputs.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The term self reliance or self help is a conception of development in which a people of a given society are mobilized in order to transform their physical, technological, political, administrative, economic and social environments, for their general well being and those of other communities. It is a development strategy which relies mainly on peoples' ability to bring about self generating and self sustaining socio-economic and political system which is problem searching, problem leaving and problem solving.

As a conceptual tool, self reliance or self help has both ideological and instrumental dimensions and as an ideology, it entails development of a perspective of "we" consciousness in a people that their destiny and survival lies in their determined and sustained efforts rather than on the effort and directions of other people who have transformed their environment for their own well- being.

When self help or self reliance is internalized as an ideology, it leads to the recovery of peoples self respect, self confidence, self worth and self actualization and as an instrument for accountability, the pace of all aspects of national development; self reliance is used to shake off inertia in people.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section attempts a detailed analysis and interpretation of the data obtained from the field investigation regarding the topic "Evaluation of self help community development projects in Zungeru in Niger state Nigeria."

Income of Respondents and their levels of Involvement in Community Development:

On the income of the respondents in the study area, the field survey result indicated that there is an average monthly income of ₦24,000:00 for the community and 46% of the respondents earned less than ₦15, 000: 00 per month, 27% earned between ₦ 15, 000: 00 and under ₦30,000: 00, while 16% and 11% of the respondents earned ₦30,000: 00 and under ₦ 45,000: 00 and ₦ 45,000: 00 and above per month respectively.

Table 1: Monthly Income and the Level of Contribution to Community Development Projects

Monthly Income of Respondents				Involvement in Community Development		
Income Per Month(#'000)	Frequency	Percentage	Involvement level	Frequency	Percentage	
Less than ₦15,000:00	276	46	Individuals	24	4	
₦15,000 and under ₦30,000	162	27	Age grades	96	16	
₦30,000 and under ₦45,000	96	16	Trade unions	192	32	
Above ₦45,000	66	11	CBOs	288	48	
Total	600	100	Total	600	100	

Source: Field Survey August, 2012

With regards to the degree of level of involvement of different institutions in the study area in community development efforts, table 1 indicates that individual and age grade efforts is 4% and 16 % while Trade unions and Community Based Organizations (CBOs) have 32% and 48% responses respectively.

Types of Self Help Development Projects:

In order to ascertain the various forms of community development projects in the study area, the following responses emerged.

Fig. 2: Types of Self – help Community Development Projects
Source: Field Survey August, 2012

The result indicates that the construction of community culverts has 174 (29%) responses, while town hall and water projects had 84 (14%) responses each. On electricity projects, only 78 (13%) accorded priority to its provision in the study area. It is important to emphasize that other projects such as schools construction, market stall provision, mosque construction and others had 180 (30%) responses.

Traditional Title Holders in Community Development Efforts:

The role of traditional title holders in community development efforts in the community can not be over emphasized. The survey result indicated that 30 (5%) of the 600 respondents agreed that they are traditional title holders and they are involved in community development efforts in the area. Their various contributions towards community efforts in the community are spelt out in figure 3.

The role of traditional title holders in bringing about grassroots development initiatives was overwhelmingly expressed in figure 3 which shows that 270 (45%) of the roles played by title holders is the bringing together of people within their domain for developmental purposes. A total of 138 (23%) and 108 (18%) of the 600 respondents asserted that traditional title holders give financial aids and linkage between people and government respectively, while 54 (9%) stood for other roles they perform in the society.

Fig. 3: Traditional Title Holders in Community Development
Source: Field Survey August, 2012

The Government in Community Development:

The role of the government at community development in the study area is minimal. The government has contributed in various capacities but small to provide finance for projects construction (42%), giving technical aid (8%), providing materials for construction work (10%). At some other levels, as shown in table 2, 7% government contribution is for the purpose of rehabilitation of community facilities such as schools, health centres, drainage network etc.

Table 2: Contributions of government in Community Development

Contributions	Frequency	Percentages
Financial Support	252	42
Technical Aids	48	8
Materials for Construction	60	10
Rehabilitation of community facilities.	42	7
Others	198	33
Total	600	100

Source: Field Survey August, 2012

Community Based Organization in Community Development:

At the community level, five (5) major organizations were identified as contributing to the overall development of the study area in terms of construction of community projects. Amongst these organizations are the Niger State Polytechnics Staff Association, Zungeru (NSPSAZ), Traders Associations Zungeru (TAZ), One Family Association, Zungeru (OFAZ), Spare Parts Dealers Associations, Zungeru Youths Association (ZUYA) and others as indicated in table 3.

Table 3: Community Based Organizations in Zungeru

CBOs	Activities	Location
Niger State Polytechnic Staff Association (NSPSAZ)	Water Projects, Bore holes, Community wells.	Zungeru
Traders Association Zungeru (TAZ)	Culvert construction, provision of electric poles, Construction of locked up shops,	Zungeru
One Family Zungeru (OFAZ)	N.A	Zungeru
Spare Parts Dealers Association	Repair of market stores	Zungeru
Zungeru Youths Association (ZUYA)	Town hall construction, schools repair, transformers provision	Zungeru
Others	N.A	Zungeru

Source: Field Survey August, 2012

Community Based Organizations Projects Execution and Costing:

Further investigation has shown that many community based projects have been executed and /or on going by these various community based organizations in the study area such as sinking of boreholes, wells etc, while trade association have constructed culverts, provided electricity for neighbourhoods in the community and as well involved in the provision of market shops. At some other levels, Town halls, transformers, schools repairs, construction of block of classrooms etc have been provided by other organizations in the community.

A study of the financial implication of the numerous projects executed by some community based organizations between the years 2008 and 2012 in the study area, as shown in table 4, a total of Thirty three million naira only (N33, 000, 000 :=) has so far been expended on community projects such as school repairs and construction of culverts in various locations in the town.

Table 4: Projects Execution and Costing (2008 - 2012)

NGOs	Projects Executed									Date/Project (millions)			Costs (N)	Location of Projects
	Water Project	Electricity	Drainage	Schools	Town Hall	Streets Repair	Others	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012		
NSZPSAZ	x					x		3.2					1.5	Angwa Seriki
T.A.Z			x		x				2.3			5.2		Angwa Madaki
ZUYA				x				3.5						Angwa Seriki
OFAZ						x	x			2.5			4.1	Zungeru
SPDAZ			x									4.5		Angwa Madaki
Others		x									6.2			Zungeru
Total	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	6.7	2.3	8.7	9.7	5.6		

Source: Field Survey August, 2012

A further examination of table 4 shows that in 2008 and 2009, #6.7million and #2.3million each was spent for community projects. On the other hand, in the years 2010 and 2011 the money spent on community projects in the community increased tremendously to #8.7million and #9.7million respectively and dropped to #5.6million in 2012.

Plate 1: A bore hole provided by CBOs in Zungeru

Plate 2: Locked up Shops by CBOs in Zungeru

Plate3: Transformer Provided by CBOs in Zungeru

Plate 4: Commercial Shops by CBO in Zungeru

Plate 5: Drainage channelization in Zungeru by CBOs

Plate 6: Primary School construction in Zungeru

Plate 7: Community Town hall in Zungeru by CBOs

Satisfaction with Community Projects:

As part of the appraisal of community projects in the study area, respondents were asked to indicate their satisfaction with self - help projects provision in their respective neighbourhoods as inadequate, fairly adequate, adequate and very adequate and the responses are tabulated in table 5.

Table 5: The degree of Satisfaction with Community Projects Execution

Projects/Satisfaction		Inadequate	Fairly adequate	Adequate	Very adequate	Total
Water Project	Frequency	438	120	30	12	600
	%	73	20	5	2	100
Electricity	Frequency	378	120	42	40	600
	%	63	20	7	10	100
Culvert	Frequency	234	288	68	18	600
	%	39	48	10	3	100
Town hall	Frequency	324	132	72	72	600
	%	54	22	12	12	100
School project	Frequency	384	168	36	12	600
	%	64	28	6	2	100
Street repair	Frequency	294	156	108	42	600
	%	49	26	18	7	100
Shop Construction	Frequency	258	138	144	60	600
	%	43	23	24	10	100
Others	Frequency	408	108	54	30	600
	%	68	18	9	5	100

Source: Field Survey August, 2012

On the degree of the citizen's satisfaction with the level of self -help community projects developments in the study area, the following observations were made.

The water project had 258 (43%), 138 (23%), 144 (24%) and 60 (10%) as inadequate, fairly adequate, adequate and very inadequate, while electricity supply projects had 408 (68%), 108 (18%), 54 (9%) and 30 (5%) as inadequate, fairly adequate and very adequate respectively.

For culvert construction projects the responses were 438 (73%), 120 (20%), 30 (5%) and 12 (2%), and 348 (63%), 120 (20%) 42 (7%) and 60 (10%) for town hall projects respectively. As regards school projects the responses were 234 (54%), 132 (22%), 72 (12%), 384 (64%), and streets repairs had 168 (28%), 36 (6%), 12 (2%) and 12 (12%) for inadequate, fairly adequate, adequate and very adequate respectively.

Lastly, for commercial shops construction and community projects summarized as others the assessment by respondents was 384 (64%), 168 (28%), 36 (6%), 12 (2%) and 294 (49%), 156 (26%), 108 (18%) and 42 (7%) were adjudged as inadequate, fairly adequate, adequate and very adequate respectively.

Problems of Self – Help Community Projects Efforts

Any developmental effort is usually associated with certain problems (Compass Nigeria, 2008). This was evident in the study of community self help projects carried out in Zungeru. Numerous development problems were found to be associated with most of the projects executed or on – going in the study area, they include financial constraints, political /social constraints, lack of co – operation, mismanagement of projects funds and others as indicated in figure 4.

Fig. 4: Problems associated with self help community development projects
Source: Field Survey August, 2012

Resolving the Problems of Community Development Efforts

Numerous ways were advanced by the members of the community for reducing the degree of the problems of community development efforts in the study area and topmost in the various suggestions given by the respondents on the ways of resolving the problems of community development efforts in the study area was the provision of adequate financial assistances for rapid community development projects (24.7%), while co-operative facilities provision, improvement in government policies, Technical aids, provision of lay out designs and urban plans had (25.5%), (20.5%), (12.7%) and (16.6%) responses respectively as shown in figure 5.

Fig.5: The ways forward for community development projects in Zungeru
Source: Author’s Analysis August, 2012

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The summary of the major findings in the study are as follows

- 276 (46%) of the 600 respondents earned below #15, 000 = monthly, 162 (27%) earned between #15, 000 = and below #30, 000 = monthly. And 96 (16%) earned between # 30, 000 and below #45, 000 monthly and 66 (11%) of the respondents earned above #45, 000 per month. The average monthly income in the study area is # 24, 000.
- That Traditional title holders and the government complement the efforts of CBOs in the community infrastructural development efforts in the study area as indicated in figure 4 and table 2.
- The government contribution towards community development has been very insignificant as little impact has been recorded in terms of financial aids (42%), Technical aids for projects execution (8%), material provision for construction (10%) and rehabilitation of community facilities (7%).
- Five (5) major CBOs are recognized in the study area: Niger State Polytechnic Staff Association, Zungeru (NSPSAZ); Traders Association, Zungeru (TAZ); Zungeru Youths Association, Zungeru (ZUYA); One Family Association, Zungeru (OFAZ) ; and Spare Parts Dealers Association, Zungeru (SPDAZ).
- That the level of involvement of these CBOs in community development efforts are well reflected in the areas of water projects, culverts construction, town halls works, electricity projects, retail shops provision and school repairs.
- That between 2008 and 2012, a total of Thirty three million naira (33,000,000 =) was expended on community development projects by Community Based Organizations and governments in the area.
- The problems associated with community development efforts in the area include financial constraints, social – political problems, lack of co – operation, mismanagement of projects funds and others such as lack of technical aids.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Recommendations

Many community projects have been executed in the study area with a lot of constraints such as inadequate funding, mismanagement of projects funds, social political problems and lack of co-operation among stakeholders in the provision of community projects. The following are therefore recommended to bring about accelerated sustainable development in the study area.

- For an effective lasting solution to the problems of gross inadequate provision of community facility provision in the study area, it is recommended that physical planning must be embraced since physical planning involves the creation of functionally efficient and aesthetically friendly environment for living, working, circulation and recreation.
- Problems of land acquisition for community project development should be resolved through preparation of community Lay out plans, Action plans and Developments in the host communities.
- Funding of projects was found to be a major constraint to community development efforts in the study area. It is therefore recommended that efforts should be made by the various CBOs in the community to embark on viable money fetching community projects that can generate funds for continued functioning of their organizations.
- With regard to mismanagement of community projects funds, it is recommended that practicable check and balances in the form of committees of men of proven integrity should be put in place by such community based organizations to avoid mismanagement of funds.
- With respect to funding of community projects, the government should make available institutions that extend credit facilities at very low interest rate to CBOs for projects development in our communities.
- Through legislation, micro finance institutions should be encouraged to locate in rural areas to extend micro credits and soft loan schemes, with less interest and friendly collateral facilities to assist CBOs to improve and expand their economic base and for the overall sustainable development of our communities.
- It was also seen that most of the community projects have problem of adequate technical aids supervision which made the projects sub standard. It is therefore recommended that qualified and experienced technical experts be employed to supervise community projects from inception stage to completion.

- Above all, the Federal government should encourage and assist the states and L.G.As and communities in infrastructural development drives in the provision of community roads, boreholes, water supply and educational facilities projects.

Conclusions

Community development is an essential instrument for sustainable development of our communities, especially in a developing country such as Nigeria. It is however, important to note that sustainable community development in Nigeria is faced with numerous constraints and among which are inadequate financial funding, mismanagement of projects funds, dearth of technical aids for project execution, social political problems and inadequate government policies towards sustainable community development. It is assumed that a careful study and understanding and implementation of the recommendations will in no doubt bring in no small way about accelerated sustainable development and general improvement in the standard of living of the people in the study area.

REFERENCES

- Anuncha H.O (1992). The Concept and Definition of Rural Infrastructure Development A paper presented at the 5th Annual Workshop on Physical Planning and Rural Infrastructural Development . Community Development (2008). <http://www.tomywdlolv.net/ehdc/cdvep/cdreplis.html> Retrieved 24/4/2008
- Egunjobi, T. (1997). Regional Appraisal of Rural Infrastructural Planning. A paper presented at the 5th Annual Workshop on Physical Planning and Rural Infrastructural Development
- Frischmann, B.M (2007). Infrastructure Commons in Economic Perspectives. An Article Publish in First Monday Vol. 12 No.6 2006
- Hornby, A.S (2005). Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary 6th edition Oxford University Press
- Ibrahim, B (2008). Appraisal of Self Help Community Development Projects as a Strategy for Community Development in Zungeru Town of Niger State; An unpublished first degree Dissertation submitted to the Department of Urban and Regional Planning Federal University of Technology Minna
- Idachaba, F.S (2005). Rural Infrastructures in Nigeria; Basic needs of the Rural Majority Federal Development Habitat International Vol. 6 No. ½ pp 7 – 14
- Isma, K. (1993). Planning in Rural Environment M. Graw Hill Book Co New York
- James, D.W (2003): United Nations Development. Community Development in Developing Countries
- Koinyan, L.D (1993). Integrated Rural Development as at the formation of National Development. Spectrum Books Ltd Ibadan Nigeria
- Kunle, A. (2004). Transportation Planning in Readings in Urban and Regional Planning edited by Tunde Agbola Macmillan Nigeria Publishers Limited, Nigeria pp257
- Robinson, H. and Bamford C.G (1978). "Aspect" Geographies Geography of Transport published by MacDonald and Evans Ltd. PP 339
- Max Lock (1980). Minna Master Final Report Max Lock Group Nigeria Ltd, Minna.
- Muhammed, D. (1994). Zungeru: The Forgotten Capital of Northern Nigeria. NPC (1991): National Population Commission Results and Population Estimates (2012)
- Nwosu, A.S (1987). Self Help Projects in Rural Infrastructure Development. A Case of Fiditi Town in Oyo State Ilesanmi Publishers Ltd Ibadan
- Ogbuozobe, J.E (2000). Community Based Organizations in the Provision of Social Services in Ibadan Metropolitan Areas Spectrum Publishers Ltd Ibadan, Nigeria
- Ogbonna, E.F (1999). Community Development in Amasiri Community in Imo State Nigeria
- Ola, E, Aluko (2004). Social Services Planning in Nigeria in Readings in Urban and Regional Planning edited by Tunde Agbola Macmillan Nigeria Publishers Limited, Nigeria pp294 - 295
- Omokhogbo O.O (2005). Infrastructural Provision as a tool for Community Development: A Case Study of Maitumbi in Bosso Local Government Area of Niger state; An unpublished under graduate project submitted to Urban and Regional Planning Department Federal University of Technology Minna
- Phillips, A.O (1997). *Population and Development in Nigeria, 1998 – 2010*, NISER Monograph Series No.16 Nigeria Institute of Social and Economic Research (NICER), Ibadan
- Sanusi, Y.A (2005). Zungeru: A study in Natural Heritage Preservation
- Sudhir, W. Yashir (1995). Rural Services, Rural Infrastructure and Regional Development in India. *The Geographical Journal* Vol.161, No.2 July 1995
- WB (1994). World Bank report paper 1994